

Thermodynamic analysis of a solar-fed heat upgrade system using the reverse air Brayton cycle

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Abstract

This analysis focuses on exploiting solar energy to meet industrial energy needs. It is based on upgrading solar heat production using surplus electricity from renewables to generate high-temperature industrial process heat. The approach involves the use of efficient evacuated flat plate solar thermal collectors coupled with a thermal storage tank to power a reverse air Brayton heat pump for high-temperature heat production. A Matlab algorithm has been developed to dynamically analyse energy balances across the system. The analysis is conducted for the location of Komotini, Greece and the results regard the operation of a system for a typical summer week. For the baseline design point with a 1000 m² collecting area and 50 m³ thermal tank volume, the average daily process heat production for the industry is 8.63 MWh, while the average daily coefficient of performance for the heat pump is 1.478. Moreover, the present work includes results regarding the parametric performance of the system for different combinations of collecting area and thermal tank volume. It was demonstrated that with the optimization of ST collector area and TES tank volume, the daily average COP can be increased up to 23.1%. Finally, the influence of the units of transfer area of the heat exchangers on the coefficient of performance has been investigated.

Keywords

Solar Energy, Heat pump, Reverse Brayton cycle, Waste heat recovery, Industrial process

1. Introduction

In the EU-27, the industrial sector ranks as the third highest in greenhouse gas emissions, generating 720 million tons of CO₂ equivalent each year [1]. In 2020, its energy consumption was 9.68 EJ, constituting 26.1% of the total final energy usage. About 80% of this energy is utilized for heat production at various temperatures [1]. High-temperature heat upgrade is necessary in many industrial applications such as in printing and the food and beverage sector [2], with approximately 75% of this energy supplied from fossil fuels [3]. Therefore, it is evident, that technological solutions that could provide the required heat, while maintaining the CO₂ emissions low would be beneficial to the industry and environment.

Integrating renewable energy sources into heat upgrade units can enhance their efficiency and enable the generation of high-temperature process heat. Solar thermal systems, in particular, are seen as promising for creating sustainable and effective industrial heat upgrade solutions. Furthermore, the implementation of various types of heat pumps has been considered a viable option for energy recovery and savings. This technology has recently advanced in several ways, including the development of more sophisticated cycle designs, and enhanced performance and

reliability of cycle components [4]. As a consequence, the high-temperature heat pump (HTHP) could lift the low-grade temperature sources to heat production over 100°C [3].

An absorption heat transformer (AHT) is an efficient device for utilizing low-grade heat sources such as waste heat and solar thermal energy. It upgrades these sources into higher-temperature heat streams using a thermochemical process, typically with around 50% efficiency. Unlike absorption heat pumps, AHTs take a medium-temperature heat input and produce two output streams: one at a higher and another at a lower temperature. This process maximizes the use of input exergy to create heat with higher exergetic value, however with reduced output capacity [5].

The effectiveness of a heat pump is significantly influenced by the working fluid used. Various fluids have been explored for this purpose. The optimal fluid for a specific application is determined by factors such as the operating temperatures, power scales, and the design of the components involved [4]. Typically, the working fluids in high-temperature heat pumps include various hydrocarbons (like pentane and butane), fluorocarbons (such as R134a and R245fa), and simpler molecule fluids including ammonia or CO₂ [3]. The choice of fluids has been evolving over recent decades, partly driven by environmental considerations leading to the restriction of some fluids due to their negative environmental impacts [6]. Zhang et al. [7] highlight the need for research and development of new refrigerants, particularly for high-temperature heat pumps. This is because there is currently a limited selection of fluids that are both suitable for high temperatures and environmentally friendly.

The temperature range of the available heat has also a crucial role. For medium-temperature applications, Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) systems have been effective, especially in large-scale settings. In the past decade, significant research has been conducted to develop ORC systems for mid and small-scale applications. However, for high-temperature waste heat sources, ORC technology is less appealing due to the lower chemical stability and higher flammability of the working fluids. By contrast, bottoming thermodynamic cycles using supercritical carbon dioxide (sCO₂) are emerging as a promising alternative for harnessing high-temperature waste heat [8], [9]. The advantage of sCO₂ technology lies in the unique properties CO₂ exhibits in its supercritical state, particularly near its critical point. The cycle typically follows a Joule-Brayton configuration [10]. This technology becomes particularly appealing when applied to scenarios where heat is rejected at temperatures over 400°C [8]. This capability has led to various studies exploring the application of sCO₂ cycles across various high-temperature heat recovery systems. Manente et al. [11] demonstrated the efficiency of s-CO₂ power cycle layouts for the recovery of waste heat between 400 and 800°C, showcasing heat recovery efficiency in the range of 17.8% - 28.5% for a 1 MW system. For the same net power (1 MW), Laleh et al. [12] proposed a sCO₂ power cycle with recompression fuelled by biomass for the recovery of waste heat from the combustion chamber. Khan et al. [13] compared two multi-generation systems based on sCO₂ Brayton cycles, finding that the recompression configuration outperforms the regenerative one with 6.55 MW higher net output power, 4.06% higher exergy efficiency, and lower economic costs. Song et al. [14] proposed four combined sCO₂-ORC system configurations for hybrid solar and geothermal power generation for the conditions of Sevilla, Spain, concluding that the best configuration achieves a 45% higher net power output of 2.94 MW compared to a standalone sCO₂ plant. Recently, Zhao et al. [15] investigated the performance of sub-megawatt-scale sCO₂ Brayton cycles

under fluctuating loads, finding that optimal parameter matching can improve cycle efficiency by up to 31.97% and net power by up to 76.42% for a 0.1 MWe system, and by 13.89% and 26.69% for a 1 MWe system.

Furthermore, the utilisation of sCO₂ cycles across various high-temperature heat recovery scenarios has also led to efforts in the development of new dynamic control and optimisation strategies. Hai et al. [16] developed a multi-objective optimization strategy to enhance a multi-generation system incorporating sCO₂ cycles, achieving energy efficiency in the order of 46% while generating 130.068 MW of power output. Delsoto et al. [17] investigated the power output dynamics of a 10 MW sCO₂ recompression Brayton cycle plant under variable solar conditions, demonstrating that an active control system for fluid mass inventory and optimized thermal energy storage can reduce auxiliary heating needs and fuel consumption by over 10%. Chen et al. [18] developed an integrated dynamic model for a supercritical CO₂ recompression cycle combined with a solid oxide fuel cell. Turja et al. [19] employed various machine-learning approaches to predict, evaluate and optimise supercritical CO₂ Power Cycles integrated with ORCs. Finally, Yang et al. [20] introduced a novel superstructure method for optimizing supercritical CO₂ cycles, achieving up to 21.23% and 6.94% higher net power output compared to traditional sCO₂ and steam Rankine cycles respectively at the heat source temperature of 400–600°C.

Despite the substantial and ongoing research in the field of HTHP [21], [22], heat pumps that operate with the Brayton cycle with air as the working medium for the utilization of waste/solar heat have not been investigated thoroughly, due to the use of refrigerants [23]. Air has no environmental impact and is very simple to process. Furthermore, an important advantage of air as the working medium lies in the fact that the compression with industrial compressors could yield temperatures higher than 200°C and up to 300°C. As such, the integration of a Brayton cycle with air as the working medium on a high-temperature heat pump for utilizing waste/solar heat could be beneficial for the industry and the environment.

The aim of this work focuses on exploiting solar energy to meet industrial energy needs and it has been conducted in the context of the EU-funded research project SOLINDARITY [24]. It explores upgrading solar heat production using surplus electricity from renewables to generate industrial process heat. The approach involves the use of highly efficient evacuated flat plate solar thermal collectors coupled with a thermal storage tank to power a reverse air Brayton heat pump for high-temperature heat production. The novelty of this work is the use of a heat pump that operates with a reverse air Brayton cycle and so it is possible to produce useful heat at high temperatures. In contrast, the conventional heat pumps that operate with typical refrigerants (e.g. R134a, R600, R290, etc.) cannot produce useful heat in high temperatures above 200°C [23], [25] and so the present system gives a sustainable solution to this problem. Furthermore, no industrial scale applications of solar-assisted HTHP have been reported in the literature [23] with the use of solar-assisted heat pumps for low-medium heat upgrade mainly for agricultural and marine products drying [26]. The exploitation of solar irradiation increases the performance due to the higher exergy input in the system. Moreover, in the framework of the present study, the effect of the system components are parametrically investigated for the optimization of the COP of the system. With the proposed concept, optimal utilization of solar power is achieved and therefore it could be a promising technology for high-temperature heat upgrade in the industrial sector for achieving sustainability.

2. Materials and Methods

Fig. 1 shows the studied system, which integrates solar thermal (ST) collectors coupled with a thermal energy storage (TES) tank. The ST collectors The TES tank supplies heat to an HTHP operating on a reverse air Brayton cycle. This design is part of the SOLINDARITY project [24] under the EU Horizon program, aimed at efficiently upgrading heat in various industrial sectors. The ST collectors that will be used, are high vacuum flat solar collectors for pressurized (10 bar) hot water generation at a temperature of up to 180°C. The ST collectors are manufactured by TVP Solar [27] a technological partner of the SOLINDARITY project. More specifically, one of the demonstration sites of the project is the Komotini Paper Mill, located in Komotini, Greece. For this specific case, a constant air flow rate of 8.23 kg/s is required to be upgraded from 150°C to 195°C on a 24/7 basis.

Figure 1. HTHP cycle configuration including solar thermal system, storage tank and heat pump

The HTHP operates on a reverse Brayton cycle and includes three heat exchangers (HEX), a compressor, and a turbine, using air as the working medium as presented in Fig.1. The objective of the cycle is to raise the temperature of a given medium in HEX-3. To achieve that the stored heat in the TES tank heats the air in HEX-1, which is further heated in HEX-2. The compressor, powered by electricity, then increases the air's temperature. After passing through HEX-3, the air passes through the turbine, generating power, and cycles back to HEX-1. The shaft that couples the compressor and the turbine is driven with electricity.

2.1. Solar Field

For the calculation of the solar energy of each ST collector the global solar irradiation (G_T) should be determined. For the calculation of G_T for any given longitude, latitude and solar conditions the following methodology is used [28]:

The local solar time is in general different from the local clock time and their relation can be calculated as follows:

$$[\text{local solar time}] = [\text{local clock time}] + ET - 4 \cdot (l_{st} - l_{local}) \quad (1)$$

where (l_{st}) is the local clock time meridian, (l_{local}) is the local longitude and

$$ET = 9.87 \sin 2B - 7.53 \cos B - 1.5 \sin B \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where } B = \frac{360(n - 81)}{364} \quad (3)$$

and (n) is the day number (i.e. $n=1$ for 1 January).

In addition, G_T is defined, using the isotropic model [29], as follows:

$$G_T = G_{b,T} + G_{d,T} + G_{r,T} \quad (4)$$

where ($G_{b,T}$) is the beam solar irradiation, ($G_{d,T}$) is the diffused solar irradiation and ($G_{r,T}$) is the ground reflection irradiation.

For the calculation of $G_{b,T}$ the direct normal irradiation ($G_{b,N}$) and the incident angle (θ) are required. Therefore:

$$G_{b,T} = G_{b,N} \cdot \cos\theta \quad (5)$$

The incident angle can be calculated from the following equation:

$$\cos\theta = \cos\alpha \cdot \cos(\alpha_s - \alpha_w) \cdot \sin\beta + \sin\alpha \cdot \cos\beta \quad (6)$$

where:

- α is the solar altitude angle that can be calculated as follows:

$$\sin\alpha = \sin L \cdot \sin\delta + \cos L \cdot \cos\delta \cdot \cosh_s \quad (7)$$

also $\alpha = 90 - \theta_z$ where θ_z is the zenith angle.

- δ is the solar declination angle that is defined below:

$$\delta = 23.45^\circ \sin \frac{360^\circ(284 + n)}{365} \quad (8)$$

- h_s is the hour angle and is defined as follows:

$$h_s = \frac{[\text{minutes from local solar noon}]}{4 \frac{\text{deg}}{\text{min}}} \quad (9)$$

- α_s is the solar azimuth that can be defined as follows:

$$\sin\alpha_s = \cos\delta \frac{\sin h_s}{\cos\alpha} \quad (10)$$

- α_w is the collector surface azimuth angle
- β is the collector surface tilt angle
- L is the local latitude angle

The diffuse solar irradiation on the collector is defined from the horizontal diffuse irradiation $G_{d,h}$ as follows:

$$G_{d,T} = G_{d,h} \frac{1 + \cos\beta}{2} \quad (11)$$

The irradiation due to the ground reflection can be defined from the following equation:

$$G_{r,T} = \rho_r \cdot (G_{b,N} \sin\alpha + G_{d,h}) \frac{1 - \cos\beta}{2} \quad (12)$$

where (ρ_r) is the ground reflectance that is typically assumed to be equal to 0.2, as a usual value.

Therefore, from Eq.(1)-(12) G_T can be determined for any given longitude and latitude and weather conditions on the ST collectors installation and consequently the solar energy (Q_{sol}) can be calculated from the following equation:

$$Q_{sol} = A_c \cdot G_T \quad (13)$$

where A_c is the collector area. The useful heat of the collector can be obtained from:

$$\frac{Q_u}{A_c} = n_{0,b} \cdot K_\theta(\theta) \cdot G_T - c_1(T_{c,in} - T_{amb}) - c_2(T_{c,in} - T_{amb})^2 \quad (14)$$

where (T_a) is the ambient temperature while ($n_{0,b}$), (c_1) and (c_2) are the zero, linear and quadratic loss coefficients respectively which are obtained from the manufacturer of the ST collectors. In this work, these values are $n_{0,b} = 0.737$, $c_1 = 0.504 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ and $c_2 = 0.006 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}^2$ according to the Test report of the solar collector [30].

$K_\theta(\theta)$ is the incident angle modifier which can be calculated from the following relation:

$$K_\theta(\theta) = 1 - b_0 \left(\frac{1}{\cos\theta} - 1 \right) \quad (15)$$

where b_0 is a coefficient that is equal to 0.09 so that $K_\theta(50^\circ) = 0.95$, according to the ST collectors manufacturer [27].

Therefore, the thermal efficiency of the collector can be defined with respect to the solar incident angle and as a consequence with respect to time from the following equation:

$$n_{th} = \frac{Q_u}{Q_{sol}} \quad (16)$$

The useful heat (Q_u) is absorbed by the water in each collector leading to an increase in its temperature that can be calculated as:

$$Q_u = \dot{m}_c \cdot C_{p,w} \cdot (T_{c,out} - T_{c,in}) \quad (17)$$

where (\dot{m}_c) is the mass flow rate of each collector, ($C_{p,w}$) is the specific heat capacity of water, while ($T_{c,in}$) and ($T_{c,out}$) is the inlet and outlet temperature of the water in the collector respectively.

2.2. Thermal Energy Storage (TES) tank

The TES tank is a common solution in the industry to store heat during the day. The thermal equilibrium of the TES tank can be calculated taking into account the heat input from the collectors, the heat rejected from the tank in order to facilitate the required load and the heat losses to the ambient environment. The TES tank is modelled with the mixing zone modelling according to similar studies in the literature [31]. As a consequence, the tank is split into N thermal zones where a uniform temperature is considered for each thermal zone. The first zone (Zone-1) is the zone with the highest temperature while the last zone (Zone-N) is the zone with the lowest. The initial TES temperature is (T_0) and is considered to be uniform along the tank.

From the thermal equilibrium at Zone-1, Zone-2 (arbitrary intermediate zone) and Zone-N the following relations are obtained:

$$\frac{\rho_w V_t}{N} C_{p,w} \frac{\partial T_{st,1}}{\partial t} = f_1 \dot{m}_t C_{p,w} (T_{c,out} - T_{st,1}) + f_2 \dot{m}_1 C_{p,w} (T_{st,2} - T_{st,1}) + \frac{U_t A_t}{N} (T_{amb} - T_{st,1}) \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{\rho_w V_t}{N} C_{p,w} \frac{\partial T_{st,2}}{\partial t} = f_1 \dot{m}_t C_{p,w} (T_{st,1} - T_{st,2}) + f_2 \dot{m}_1 C_{p,w} (T_{st,3} - T_{st,2}) + \frac{U_t A_t}{N} (T_{amb} - T_{st,2}) \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{\rho_w V_t}{N} C_{p,w} \frac{\partial T_{st,N}}{\partial t} = f_1 \dot{m}_t C_{p,w} (T_{st,N-1} - T_{st,N}) + f_2 \dot{m}_1 C_{p,w} (T_{s,out} - T_{st,N}) + \frac{U_t A_t}{N} (T_{amb} - T_{st,N}) \quad (20)$$

where (ρ_w) is the density of water in the TES, (V_t) is the tank volume, (U_t) is the heat loss coefficient of the tank, (A_t) is the surface area of the tank, (\dot{m}_1) is the mass flow rate of the load loop, ($T_{1,out}$) is the water temperature that returns to the tank from the load, (\dot{m}_t) is the total mass flow from the total number of solar collectors while ($T_{st,i}$) is the temperature of the i^{th} thermal zone.

Furthermore, it is assumed that the temperature of the mass flow that is used for the load ($T_{l,in}$) is equal to the temperature in Zone-1, while the temperature that enters the solar collectors is equal to the temperature in Zone-N. Thus, the following equations can be written:

$$T_{l,in} = T_{st,1} \quad (21)$$

$$T_{c,in} = T_{st,N} \quad (22)$$

The output load (Q_l) can be obtained from the following equation:

$$Q_l = \dot{m}_l \cdot C_{p,w} \cdot (T_{l,in} - T_{l,out}) \quad (23)$$

In Eq. (18)-(20) two control parameters, (f_1) and (f_2) are introduced. These two parameters are used in order to control the mass flow from the collector and the load. Their control is based on the following:

- The collector loop operates when the solar irradiation is greater than 100 W/m^2 in order to avoid operation at low levels of irradiation. In the case where the irradiation is higher than the determined limit $f_1 = 1$ while when the irradiation is lower $f_1 = 0$.
- The load loop is assumed to operate when the inlet water temperature is higher than 90°C . When the load loop operates $f_2 = 1$ while $f_2 = 0$ when the load loop is closed.

The pressure of water in the ST collectors is considered to be 10 bar with a saturation point of 180°C . For that reason, the ST collectors are used to provide heat in the TES tank when $T_{c,in}$ is lower than 170°C .

The temperature ($T_{l,out}$) of the water that returns to the TES tank can be calculated from Eq.(23). For the solution of the system of differential equations Eq.(18)-(20) the finite element method is implemented. For Zone-1 the time discretization is given below:

$$\frac{\partial T_{st,1}}{\partial t} = \frac{T_{st,1}^{new} - T_{st,1}^{old}}{\Delta t} \quad (24)$$

where ($T_{st,1}^{old}$) and ($T_{st,1}^{new}$) are the temperatures of the thermal zone in the previous and current time step respectively, while (Δt) is the time step. The time step should be selected accordingly with the number of thermal zones for the proper convergence of the governing equations of the system.

As a consequence, with the described method for each time step, a set of N linear equations can be derived that can be solved with the Thomas algorithm since the matrix is tridiagonal. Therefore, with the above methodology, the operation of the ST collectors and TES tank system can be described as a function of time according to the available irradiation and control parameters of the load.

2.3. High-Temperature Heat Pump

The HTHP operates with a reverse Brayton cycle. The cycle consists of three heat exchangers (HEX) a compressor and a turbine, while the working medium is air. The purpose of the cycle is to increase the temperature of a given medium in HEX-3. For that reason, the heat stored in the TES tank is used in HEX-1 to heat the air in the cycle. The air is heated further in HEX-2 before it enters the compressor which is driven by electricity. After the HEX-3 the air enters the turbine to generate power and finally returns to HEX-1. The governing equations of the HTHP cycle are given below.

The energy equilibrium in HEX-1 is described with the following equations:

$$Q_{HEX-1} = \dot{m}_l \cdot C_{p,w} \cdot (T_{l,in} - T_{l,out}) \quad (25)$$

$$Q_{HEX-1} = \dot{m}_a \cdot C_{p,a} \cdot (T_1 - T_6) \quad (26)$$

$$Q_{HEX-1} = UA_{HEX-1} \cdot \Delta T_{lm,HEX-1} \quad (27)$$

where (\dot{m}_a) is the air mass flow in the cycle, ($C_{p,a}$) is the specific heat capacity of air, (UA_{HEX-1}) is the unit transfer area of HEX-1 and ($\Delta T_{lm,HEX-1}$) is defined as follows:

$$\Delta T_{lm,HEX-1} = \frac{(T_1 - T_{l,in}) - (T_6 - T_{l,out})}{\ln\left(\frac{T_1 - T_{l,in}}{T_6 - T_{l,out}}\right)} \quad (28)$$

The energy equilibrium in HEX-2 is described with the following equations:

$$Q_{HEX-2} = \dot{m}_a \cdot C_{p,a} \cdot (T_2 - T_1) \quad (29)$$

$$Q_{HEX-2} = \dot{m}_a \cdot C_{p,a} \cdot (T_4 - T_5) \quad (30)$$

$$Q_{HEX-2} = UA_{HEX-2} \cdot \Delta T_{lm,HEX-2} \quad (31)$$

where (UA_{HEX-2}) is the unit transfer area of HEX-2 and ($\Delta T_{lm,HEX-2}$) is defined as follows:

$$\Delta T_{lm,HEX-2} = \frac{(T_4 - T_2) - (T_5 - T_1)}{\ln\left(\frac{T_4 - T_2}{T_5 - T_1}\right)} \quad (32)$$

The energy equilibrium in HEX-3 is:

$$Q_{HEX-3} = \dot{m}_s \cdot C_{p,s} \cdot (T_{s,out} - T_{s,in}) \quad (33)$$

$$Q_{HEX-3} = \dot{m}_a \cdot C_{p,a} \cdot (T_3 - T_4) \quad (34)$$

$$Q_{HEX-3} = UA_{HEX-3} \cdot \Delta T_{lm,HEX-3} \quad (35)$$

where (\dot{m}_s) is the mass flow that requires heat upgrade, ($C_{p,s}$) is the specific heat capacity of that mass, ($T_{s,out}$) and ($T_{s,in}$) are the inlet and outlet temperatures respectively, (UA_{HEX-3}) is the unit transfer area of HEX-3 and ($\Delta T_{lm,HEX-3}$) is defined as follows:

$$\Delta T_{lm,HEX-3} = \frac{(T_3 - T_{s,out}) - (T_4 - T_{s,in})}{\ln\left(\frac{T_3 - T_{s,out}}{T_4 - T_{s,in}}\right)} \quad (36)$$

In the compressor, the pressure of the air is increased from the low pressure in the cycle (p_{low}) to the high-pressure (p_{high}). Therefore, the pressure ratio (π) is calculated as below:

$$p_{high} = \pi \cdot p_{low} \quad (37)$$

The pressure ratio is considered to be equal in the compressor and in the turbine since pressure drops in the cycle are neglected. The compressor has an isentropic efficiency ($n_{is,com}$) which is determined as follows:

$$n_{is,com} = \frac{h_{3,is} - h_2}{h_3 - h_2} \quad (38)$$

where (h_2) is the specific enthalpy of air for the conditions of the state-point 2 of the cycle, (h_3) is the specific enthalpy of the air for the conditions of state point 3 while ($h_{3,is}$) is the specific enthalpy of the compression if the process is isentropic.

The required power (P_{com}) for the compression can be calculated as:

$$P_{com} = \dot{m}_a \cdot (h_3 - h_2) \quad (39)$$

The turbine has an isentropic efficiency ($n_{is,tur}$) which can be determined as follows:

$$n_{is,tur} = \frac{h_5 - h_6}{h_5 - h_{6,is}} \quad (40)$$

where (h_5) is the specific enthalpy of air for the conditions of state-point 5 of the cycle, (h_6) is the specific enthalpy of the air for the conditions of state point 6 while ($h_{6,is}$) is the specific enthalpy if the process is isentropic.

The generated power (P_{tur}) in the turbine can be calculated as:

$$P_{tur} = \dot{m}_a \cdot (h_5 - h_6) \quad (41)$$

As a consequence, the total energy equilibrium of the cycle is:

$$P_{com} + Q_{HEX-1} = P_{tur} + Q_{HEX-3} \quad (42)$$

As a consequence, the electrical power that is required to drive the shaft of the compressor and the turbine can be calculated as:

$$P_{el} = \frac{1}{n_{mot}} \left(\frac{P_{com}}{n_{m,com}} - n_{m,tur} \cdot P_{tur} \right) \quad (43)$$

where (n_{mot}), ($n_{m,com}$) and ($n_{m,tur}$) are the mechanical efficiencies of the motor, the compressor and the turbine respectively.

In the system of Eqs. (25)-(43), p_{low} , \dot{m}_l , $T_{l,in}$, \dot{m}_s , $T_{s,in}$, $T_{s,out}$ are the inputs of the system at each time step while UA_{HEX-1} , UA_{HEX-2} , UA_{HEX-3} , $n_{is,c}$, $n_{is,t}$, n_{mot} , $n_{m,com}$ and $n_{m,tur}$ are assumed to be known for a given design of the HTHP.

As a consequence, a non-linear system of 18 equations and 18 unknowns is derived that can be solved numerically as shown in Appendix A.

Finally, the (COP) of the system can be calculated as:

$$COP = \frac{Q_{HEX-3}}{P_{el}} \quad (44)$$

The average daily power outputs of the system can be obtained after the integration of the system's conditions at each time step.

2.4. Exergy performance calculations

After the calculation of the solar field, the TES tank and the conditions of the HTHP the exergy efficiency of the collectors, the HTHP the heat exchangers and the system as a whole can be calculated as follows.

The exergy efficiency of the ST collectors ($n_{\text{ex-col}}$) is calculated according to Ref. [32]:

$$n_{\text{ex-col}} = \frac{EX_u}{EX_{\text{sol}}} \quad (45)$$

where (EX_u) is the exergy of the useful solar heat and can be calculated as:

$$EX_u = \dot{m}_c \cdot C_{p,w} \cdot (T_{c,\text{out}} - T_{c,\text{in}}) - \dot{m}_c \cdot C_{p,w} \cdot T_{\text{amb}} \cdot \ln \frac{T_{c,\text{out}}}{T_{c,\text{in}}} \quad (46)$$

and (EX_{sol}) is the solar exergy flow and can be obtained from the Petela relation [33] as follows:

$$EX_{\text{sol}} = Q_{\text{sol}} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{4}{3} \cdot \left(\frac{T_{\text{amb}}}{T_{\text{sun}}} \right) - \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{T_{\text{amb}}}{T_{\text{sun}}} \right)^4 \right) \quad (47)$$

where T_{sun} is the temperature of the sun's surface and is equal to 5800K.

The exergy efficiency of the HTHP ($n_{\text{ex-HP}}$) is calculated as:

$$n_{\text{ex-HP}} = \frac{EX_{\text{out}}}{EX_{\text{in}} + P_{\text{el}}} \quad (48)$$

where (EX_{out}) is the exergy of the output and can be calculated as:

$$EX_{\text{out}} = \dot{m}_s \cdot C_{p,s} \cdot (T_{s,\text{out}} - T_{s,\text{in}}) - \dot{m}_s \cdot C_{p,s} \cdot T_{\text{amb}} \cdot \ln \frac{T_{s,\text{out}}}{T_{s,\text{in}}} \quad (49)$$

and (EX_{in}) is the exergy of the storage input and can be calculated as:

$$EX_{\text{in}} = \dot{m}_l \cdot C_{p,l} \cdot (T_{l,\text{in}} - T_{l,\text{out}}) - \dot{m}_l \cdot C_{p,l} \cdot T_{\text{amb}} \cdot \ln \frac{T_{l,\text{in}}}{T_{l,\text{out}}} \quad (50)$$

The exergy efficiency of the system as a whole ($n_{\text{ex-sys}}$) is calculated as:

$$n_{\text{ex-sys}} = \frac{EX_{\text{out}}}{EX_{\text{sol}} + P_{\text{el}}} \quad (51)$$

The exergy efficiency of HEX-1 ($n_{\text{ex-HEX-1}}$) is calculated as:

$$n_{\text{ex-HEX-1}} = \frac{EX_{6 \rightarrow 1}}{EX_{\text{in}}} \quad (52)$$

where ($EX_{6 \rightarrow 1}$) is the exergy from state-point 6 to the state-point 1 and can be calculated as:

$$EX_{6 \rightarrow 1} = \dot{m}_a \cdot C_{p,a} \cdot (T_1 - T_6) - \dot{m}_a \cdot C_{p,a} \cdot T_{\text{amb}} \cdot \ln \frac{T_1}{T_6} \quad (53)$$

The exergy efficiency of HEX-2 ($n_{\text{ex-HEX-2}}$) is calculated as:

$$n_{\text{ex-HEX-2}} = \frac{EX_{1 \rightarrow 2}}{EX_{4 \rightarrow 5}} \quad (54)$$

where ($Ex_{1\rightarrow 2}$) is the exergy from state-point 1 to the state-point 2 and can be calculated as:

$$Ex_{1\rightarrow 2} = \dot{m}_a \cdot C_{p,a} \cdot (T_2 - T_1) - \dot{m}_a \cdot C_{p,a} \cdot T_{amb} \cdot \ln \frac{T_2}{T_1} \quad (55)$$

and ($Ex_{4\rightarrow 5}$) is the exergy from state-point 4 to the state-point 5 and can be calculated as:

$$Ex_{4\rightarrow 5} = \dot{m}_a \cdot C_{p,a} \cdot (T_4 - T_5) - \dot{m}_a \cdot C_{p,a} \cdot T_{amb} \cdot \ln \frac{T_4}{T_5} \quad (56)$$

Finally, the exergy efficiency of HEX-3 ($n_{ex-HEX-3}$) is calculated as:

$$n_{ex-HEX-3} = \frac{Ex_{out}}{Ex_{3\rightarrow 4}} \quad (57)$$

where ($Ex_{3\rightarrow 4}$) is the exergy from state-point 3 to the state-point 4 and can be calculated as:

$$Ex_{3\rightarrow 4} = \dot{m}_a \cdot C_{p,a} \cdot (T_3 - T_4) - \dot{m}_a \cdot C_{p,a} \cdot T_{amb} \cdot \ln \frac{T_3}{T_4} \quad (58)$$

The daily average exergy efficiencies can be obtained after the integration of the exergy efficiencies at each time step.

2.5 Followed methodology

In order to demonstrate the dynamical response of the proposed concept the following case study was made for one of the demonstration sites of the SOLINDARITY project [24] and specifically for the ELINA Paper Mill which is located in Komotini, Greece. The parameters of the components of the ST collectors, the TES tank, the HTHP and the demonstration site requirements are given in Table 1. For the dynamical simulation of the system, a typical August week (6/8-13/8) was selected in order to investigate the effect of the proposed concept under good weather conditions. The solar irradiation and weather data were obtained from PVGIS [34] for the area of Komotini Greece (41°07'9.01" N, 25°24'19.26" E) and are presented in detail in Appendix B.

Table 1. Simulation Input Parameters

Parameter		Value
A_c	[m ²]	1000
$n_{is,c}$	[%]	85
$n_{is,t}$	[%]	80
n_{mot}	[%]	100
$n_{m,com}$	[%]	99
$n_{m,tur}$	[%]	99
\dot{m}_l	[kg/s]	3
\dot{m}_s	[kg/s]	8.233
$T_{s,in}$	[°C]	150
$T_{s,out}$	[°C]	195
UA_{HEX-1}	[W/K]	23800
UA_{HEX-2}	[W/K]	12500
UA_{HEX-3}	[W/K]	12500
U_T	[W/m ² /K]	0.5
V	[m ³]	50

In the TES tank, a total number of 10 thermal zones have been selected, after a proper sensitivity analysis. Furthermore, the time step of the simulation has been selected to 60 seconds which was determined after a proper time step independence procedure. The initial time of operation was considered to be August 6th at 00:00, while the final time of the simulation was August 12th at 23:59. The initial TES tank temperature was assumed to be 85°C. The TES tank is expected to reach higher temperatures during the operation of the HTHP, however the initial temperature was selected to be 85°C to be on the safe side. For each time step the global solar irradiation and consequently, the useful solar energy from the ST collectors was calculated. The transient thermal response of the TES tank was calculated taking into account the input from the ST collector loop and the return from the HTHP. The HTHP cycle was calculated at each time step taking into account the input temperature from the TES tank. For each time step the mass flow rate of the reverse air Brayton cycle and the pressure ratio of the compressor and turbine was calculated so that the HTHP could meet the heat upgrade requirements of the demonstration site. Due to the nonlinearity of the system of equations, the state-point temperatures of the cycle are determined with the use of the genetic algorithm as shown in detail in Appendix A. The dynamical simulation of the system is obtained with an algorithm developed in the MATLAB environment [35] that incorporates all the phenomena between the components of the system.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Analysis of the Basic Scenario

In this subsection, the performance results of the examined system and the basic scenario are presented in detail. Results regarding the energy flow and the efficiency indexes are given for the examined typical week of August. In Fig.2, the useful heat acquired from the ST collectors is presented. The ST collectors -TES tank loop is operational between approximately 07:00-18:00 when the global solar irradiation is higher than 100 W/m², as shown in Fig.B4 in Appendix B. It can be observed, that during high noon hours, the useful heat peak was between 500-570 W/m².

Figure 2. Useful heat production from the solar field with respect to time

In Fig.3 the temperature of water in the first thermal zone in the TES tank is presented with respect to time. It can be observed that during the first hours of operation, the water temperature is around 85°C reducing slightly due to the good insulation of the TES tank. In the early morning hours and when the ST collectors- TES tank loop is operational (according to the global solar irradiation control) the water temperature begins to increase. The water temperature quickly surpasses the 90°C barrier (which is the control for the operation of the TES tank-HTHP loop) and the HTHP is operational after 10:00. Furthermore, it can be observed that the water temperature in the first mixing zone maintains a value higher than 90°C, thus the HTHP is operational for the entire duration of the day which is very important since the demonstration site operates on a 24/7 basis. This result can be attributed to the large volume of the TES tank that was selected. However, the temperature of the water in the first mixing zone does not exceed a temperature above 135°C even during high noon hours. This result can also be attributed to the large volume of the TES tank signifying the importance of the ratio of the total collecting area of the ST collectors and the volume of the TES tank. As a result, the HTHP is operational on a 24-hour basis, however, the inlet temperature of the water in HEX-1 is low and consequently the efficiency of the cycle will not be the highest possible.

Figure 3. Water temperature in the first thermal zone of the TES tank

Fig.4 illustrates the heat input from the TES tank to the HEX-1 of the HTHP. During the night and in the early morning hours, the ST collectors are not operational. Therefore, since the heat input is provided only through the stored energy in the tank the tank temperature is decreasing and thus the heat input also decreases. When the ST collectors are operational (depending on their control), the temperature of the tank is increased and consequently the heat input to the HEX-1 is also increased. Initially, no heat input is provided since the load loop is not operational as the initial tank temperature is lower than 90°C. When the load loop is operational the heat input fluctuates between 70-170 kW depending on the hour of the day.

Figure 4. Heat input from HEX-1 in the HTHP with respect to time

Fig.5a depicts the required mass flow rate of the reverse air Brayton cycle, while Fig.5b illustrates the required pressure ratio of the compressor and the turbine with respect to time. When the HTHP becomes operational for the first time (first mixing zone temperature control) the required air mass flow ratio and the pressure have their highest value (due to the low water temperature in the inlet of HEX-1) at 9.84 kg/s and 1.63 respectively. After the initial transient day of operation, the values of the air mass flow rate and pressure ratio fluctuate between 7.65-9.05 kg/s and 1.51-1.61 respectively. The lowest values are observed during high noon hours a phenomenon that is expected since the temperature of the inlet water in HEX-1 has its highest value.

Figure 5. Air mass flow (a) and pressure ratio (b) in the HTHP with respect to time

Fig.6 shows the air temperature in the reverse Brayton cycle at six different state points with respect to time in accordance with Fig.1. The air temperature in the inlet, T_3 , and outlet, T_4 , of HEX-3 is practically steady during the entire week (after the HTHP becomes operational). In the other four state points, the air temperature fluctuates depending on the hour of the day. It can be observed that during high noon hours, the temperatures have their peak values.

Figure 6. Air temperature at different state points with respect to time

Fig.7 shows the power in the compressor, in the turbine and electricity with respect to time. The power in the compressor, the turbine and the electricity power required fluctuates between 550-790 kW, 295-430 kW and 230-320 kW respectively depending on the hour of the day. During the noon, the required electricity is lower, which is expected as the heat input from the ST collectors peaks.

Figure 7. Power in compressor, turbine and electricity with respect to time

Fig.8a shows the COP of the HTHP with respect to time, while Fig.8b depicts the daily average COP of the HTHP. As expected, the highest COP is observed at high noon hours, when the required electrical power from the PVs is lower. The COP of the system fluctuates between 1.15-1.75 depending on the hour of the day. The average daily COP of the HTHP is in the range of 1.43-1.49. The drop on the average COP of the system during the second can be attributed to the selected control of the HTHP. It is interesting to note that the global solar irradiation does not shown any significant change in the second day compared to others as shown in Appendix B. During the second day of the week, the daily average COP takes its lowest value at 1.43 a phenomenon that is attributed to the fact that the HTHP is operational from midnight to the early morning hours for the first time. In the first day during midnight the initial water temperature in the TES tank is 85°C which is below the control temperature of the TES tank-HTHP loop which is set at 90°C. Therefore, the system becomes operational in the morning after initially engaging the ST collectors-TES tank loop. In the second day midnight hours the water temperature is higher than 90°C but not as high as the following days (Fig.3). As a consequence, the TES tank-HTHP loop is operational, however the power in the compressor and as a result the required electricity is higher in the second day (Fig.7). Since, the water temperature in the first mixing zone is still low, as shown in Fig.3, the COP during the night operation is lower compared to the following days as illustrated in Fig.8a. After the second day, the daily average COP is stabilized to a value close to 1.50, with some small fluctuations caused by different solar irradiation and weather conditions as shown in Appendix B. As a consequence, the drop in the COP is attributed to the first day transient phenomena and the system is expected to operate smoothly afterwards, depending only on the environmental conditions.

Figure 8. COP of the HTHP with respect to time (a) and Daily average COP of the HTHP (b)

Fig.9 depicts the exergy efficiencies of the ST collectors, the HTHP pump and the system with respect to time. It should be noted that when the exergy efficiency of the ST collectors is zero the collectors are not operating and the HTHP works with the energy stored in the TES tank. The exergy efficiency of the ST collectors peaks at approximately 12% during the high noon hours. The exergy efficiency, after the initial transient operation (due to the initial conditions

and control) appears to have a relatively stable behaviour with a value that fluctuates between 39-45% depending on the hour of the day. On the other hand, the exergy efficiency of the system as a whole fluctuates between 10-50%, a phenomenon that can be attributed to the different electrical power required depending on the hour of the day.

Figure 9. Exergy efficiencies of the ST collectors, the HTHP and the system as a whole with respect to time

Fig.10 depicts the exergy efficiencies of the three heat exchangers of the HTHP with respect to time. It should be noted that when the exergy efficiency of the heat exchangers is zero when the HTHP is not operational. The exergy efficiency of HEX-3 is practically steady at around 89%. The exergy efficiency of HEX-1 fluctuates between 91-96% depending on the hour of the day. During high noon hours, the exergy efficiency of HEX-1 has its lowest values. The exergy efficiency of HEX-2 has the highest amplitude of fluctuation among the three heat exchangers of the HTHP and takes values between 77-89%. During high noon hours the exergy efficiency of HEX-2 peaks in contrast to HEX-1.

During the noon, the solar thermal field produces higher amount of useful heat and therefore the temperature level in the TES tank increases (Fig.3). Therefore, the heat is given to HEX-1 with a higher temperature level compared to the rest of the day. However, the air temperature level in the Brayton cycle doesn't increase proportionally. As a result, there is a higher exergy destruction in HEX-1 during the noon due to the increase in the mean temperature difference between the two streams. For the HEX-2, the exergy efficiency increase during the noon because the two streams present lower mean temperature difference. This occurs because T_1 increase significantly during the noon but T_3 and T_4 remain practically steady due to the air mass flow control for producing the required heat in HEX-3 (Fig.6). Finally, the exergy efficiency remains steady in HEX-3 since the temperatures in the inlet and outlet have a small fluctuation throughout the day.

Figure 10. Exergy efficiencies of the three heat exchangers with respect to time

To verify the HTHP model and proposed solution of the system of non-linear equations with the genetic algorithm (presented in Appendix A) we used the EBSILON Software [36]. The developed HTHP model is quasi-dynamic with a time-dependent input of the inlet in HEX-1. To compare the two models we assumed that the temperature of the water in HEX-1 was at a given time 150°C. The results of the two models are presented and compared in Table 2.

Table 2. Verification of the HTHP model

Parameter		Developed Model	EBSILON	Deviation [%]
π	[-]	1.439	1.438	0.07
COP	[-]	1.862	1.86	0.11
\dot{m}_a	[kg/s]	8.151	8.204	0.65
T_1	[°C]	145.58	145.55	0.02
T_2	[°C]	166.29	166.32	0.02
T_3	[°C]	225.32	225.16	0.07
T_4	[°C]	180.03	180.24	0.12
T_5	[°C]	159.37	159.51	0.09
T_6	[°C]	123.40	123.64	0.19
$T_{l,out}$	[°C]	135.73	135.83	0.07
P_{com}	[kW]	497.65	499.73	0.42
P_{el}	[kW]	203.05	203.72	0.33
Q_{HEX-1}	[kW]	183.52	182.46	0.58
Q_{HEX-2}	[kW]	172.09	173.56	0.85
Q_{HEX-3}	[kW]	378.12	378.19	0.02

The results are in perfect coherence and the small deviations could be attributed to numerical errors, convergence criteria and differences in the calculation of C_p values of the mediums.

3.2 Parametrical Investigation of the HTHP cycle

In order to investigate the HTHP cycle performance the following parametric case studies were considered. The parameters that were investigated are the total collecting area, the ratio of the total collector area to the volume of the TES tank and the three heat exchangers. The dynamical performance of the system was simulated with the parameters described in Table 1. The average COP and the average heat output on HEX-3 were calculated. In Table 3 and Fig.11, the average COP of the HTHP for different total collecting areas and ratios of collecting area to the tank volume are presented.

Table 3. Average COP for different total collecting areas and ratio of TES tank

Total collector area [m ²]	Ratio of total collector area to volume of TES tank [m ² /m ³]	Average COP	Average daily heat output [MWh]
500	10	1.238	7.39
	20	1.302	6.47
	30	1.356	5.79
750	10	1.313	8.60
	20	1.341	8.58
	30	1.398	7.78
1000	10	1.421	8.60
	20	1.478	8.63
	30	1.493	8.64
1250	10	1.509	8.60
	20	1.609	8.63
	30	1.645	8.64
1500	10	1.579	8.60
	20	1.727	8.63
	30	1.790	8.64

Fig.11 demonstrates how the total ST collecting area and the volume of the TES tank affect the COP of the HTHP. It is illustrated that during a typical summer week, a higher COP is achieved with an increased total collecting area and a larger ratio of collecting area to TES tank volume. For the case of a total collecting area of the ST collectors of 1500 m² and a TES tank volume of 50 m³, the average COP of the system is 1.81, which is a 23.1% increase when compared to the case of the parameters presented in Table 1. This result signifies the importance of the total collecting area and the ratio of the collecting area and the TES tank volume to the COP of the system.

Figure 11. Average COP for different collecting areas and ratio of the TES tank

Fig.12 depicts the average heating production in HEX-3 for different values of the total collecting area of the ST collectors and ratios of the total collecting area to the TES tank volume. The highest average heating production is 8.63 MWh/day which is the required heating production for a 24/7 operation of the demonstration site. As a consequence, when that value is obtained for different collecting areas and TES tank volumes the HTHP can meet the demonstration site requirements on a 24/7 basis. When that value is not reached the HTHP cannot be operational 24/7. From Fig.11 and Fig.12, it is evident that an optimal selection of the ST collecting area and TES tank volume is crucial to the efficient operation of the HTHP. As a consequence, it is important to select the appropriate TES tank volume for a given total area of ST collectors (which is expected to be a constraint in a given facility) in order to achieve both high COP and heating production. The optimal TES tank volume depends on the expected environmental conditions and working hours of the HTHP.

Figure 12. Average heating production for different collecting area and ratio of the TES tank

Fig.13 illustrates the average COP and heating production for different units of transfer area values of HEX-3. For the parameters defined in Table 1, the average COP was equal to 1.478 while the average heating production was 8.63 MWh. It can be observed that when the units of transfer area are increased the COP of the unit increases and approaches asymptotically a value near 1.80. However, the average heating production is decreased as the values of the units of transfer area of HEX-3 are increased. This phenomenon is attributed to the fact that higher values of units of transfer area lead to lower air temperature after HEX-3. Thus, the water from the TES tank returns to lower temperatures after HEX-1. As a result, the TES tank temperature during the night hours of operation decreases below the control temperature for the load loop and thus the HTHP stops its operation yielding lower heating production.

Figure 13. Average COP and heating production for different units of transfer area values of HEX-3

It is important to select the optimal units of transfer area in HEX-3 depending on the heating production requirements throughout the day. In our case study where the ELINA Paper Mill is operational 24/7, the temperature drop below the control point could occur easier especially during night hours that could stop the TES tank-HTHP loop and reduce the heating production. In our case it is shown that with a selection of $UA_{HEX-3}=15000$ W/K the COP of the system is increased without lowering the heating production. Therefore, the importance of optimizing the HEX-3 is demonstrated.

Fig.14 illustrates the average COP for different units of transfer area values of HEX-1. It can be observed that the maximum COP is obtained when UA_{HEX-1} is around 12500 W/K. Also, further increment of the units of transfer area of HEX-1 leads to lower COP. It is attributed to the fact that above a certain value, the increment in the temperature of the air in the cycle is not as significant as the temperature drop of the water in HEX-1. However, the influence of HEX-1 in the COP of the system is not as important as HEX-3.

Figure 14. Average COP for different HEX-1 designs

Fig.15 shows the average COP for different units of transfer area values of HEX-2. It can be observed that the units of transfer area of HEX-2 have a small effect on the COP of the HTHP. Thus, the increase of this parameter is not an important technique for enhancing performance.

Figure 15. Average COP for different HEX-2 designs

3.3 Discussion and future work

In the present work the concept of exploiting solar energy to meet industrial process heat needs is investigated. The novelty of this work is the use of a heat pump that operates with a reverse air Brayton cycle and so it is possible to produce useful heat at high temperatures above 200°C that is required in many industrial applications. In contrast, the conventional heat pumps that operate with typical refrigerants (e.g. R134a, R600, R290, etc.) cannot produce useful heat in high temperatures above 200°C and so the present system gives a sustainable solution to this problem. The novelty of our work and in general the EU SOLINDARITY project is to utilize solar energy to operate a reverse Brayton air heat pump. The integration of the system components (ST collectors, TES tank and reverse air Brayton cycle heat pump) to achieve high temperature heat upgrade for industrial purposes is a novelty in the literature. With the proposed concept, optimal utilization of solar power is achieved and therefore it could be a promising technology for high-temperature heat upgrade in the industrial sector for achieving sustainability. The proposed concept is interesting, however some issues should be further investigated and improved. The ideas for future work are:

- Conduct a generalised optimization of the components of the system for achieving the highest COP on an annual basis.
- Investigate in depth the correlation between the average COP of the system and the average heating production to achieve the most efficient design.
- Optimize the control of the TES tank-HTHP loop (water temperature in the inlet of HEX-1) to achieve the highest average heating production while maintaining high COP values.
- Investigate the effectiveness of the system in different demonstration sites, as part of the SOLINDARITY project. The other demonstration sites of the project have different solar irradiation and weather data, heat upgrade requirements and operating hours. Proving the efficiency of the proposed system in different scenarios could be highly beneficial for the industry and the environment since it would establish an effective method for high-temperature heat upgrade in the industrial sector by exploiting solar energy.

4. Conclusions

In the present work, a novel heat upgrade system that combines ST collectors with a TES tank coupled to a reverse air Brayton heat pump is proposed to produce industrial process heat. A simulation was carried out for the Paper Mill located in Komotini, Greece which is a demonstration site of the SOLINDARITY EU project. In this plant, a constant air flow rate of 8.23 kg/s needs to be upgraded from 150°C to 195°C on a 24/7 basis. For a typical summer week, the daily average COP of the HTHP is 1.478 while the heat production is 8.63 MWh. Furthermore, the exergy efficiencies of the ST collectors, the HTHP the heat exchangers and the system as a whole have been calculated. In addition, a parametric investigation regarding the total collector area and the TES tank volume has been conducted. It was demonstrated that the total collecting area of the ST collectors and the ratio of the collecting area to TES tank volume have a crucial effect on the COP and the operation of the system on a 24/7 basis. The COP of the system can be increased by as much as 23.1% with an optimal selection of the total collecting area of the ST collectors and the TES tank volume. Finally, an investigation on the influence of the units of transfer area in the three HEXs on the system's COP was performed. It was found that the HEX-3 has an important impact on the system's COP.

Appendix A – Methodology for solving the non-linear equation system

For the solution of the system of Eqs. (25)-(43) at each time step the following process is implemented since the system is nonlinear. The air mass flow \dot{m}_a and the pressure ratio π will be assumed for each time step. The convergence of the method will be achieved with the use of a nonlinear programming solver [37] and specifically the fmincon function in MATLAB environment [38] that will significantly reduce the computational cost.

Initially, from the Eqs. (33)-(36) and the input parameters of Table 1 that describe the operation of the HEX-3, the air temperatures T_3 and T_4 can be determined by implementing the NTU method [39] as follows:

$$C_{out} = \dot{m}_s \cdot C_{p,s} \quad (A.1)$$

$$C_a = \dot{m}_a \cdot C_{p,a} \quad (A.2)$$

$$C_{min} = \min(C_{out}, C_a) \quad (A.3)$$

$$C_{max} = \max(C_{out}, C_a) \quad (A.4)$$

$$NTU_{HEX-3} = \frac{UA_{HEX-3}}{C_{min}} \quad (A.5)$$

As a consequence, the efficiency of the heat exchanger (e_{HEX-3}) can be calculated as:

$$e_{HEX-3} = \frac{1 - e^{-\left(1 - \frac{C_{min}}{C_{max}}\right) \cdot NTU_{HEX-3}}}{1 - \frac{C_{min}}{C_{max}} e^{-\left(1 - \frac{C_{min}}{C_{max}}\right) \cdot NTU_{HEX-3}}} \quad (A.6)$$

As a result, the temperature T_3 and T_4 can be calculated from the following equations since Q_{HEX-3} is an input and can be calculated from Eq. (33) and the parameters given in Table 1.

$$T_3 = T_{s,in} + \frac{C_a \cdot Q_{HEX-3}}{e_{HEX-3} \cdot C_{min} \cdot \dot{m}_a \cdot C_{p,a}} \quad (A.7)$$

$$T_4 = T_3 - \frac{Q_{HEX-3}}{\dot{m}_a \cdot C_{p,a}} \quad (A.8)$$

After the calculation of T_3 the air temperature T_2 can be calculated from Eq.(38) iteratively. The numerical method that was implemented is the fixed point numerical algorithm and the flowchart for the calculation of T_2 is presented in Fig. (A.1).

Figure A.1: Flowchart for the calculation of T_2

After the calculation of the air temperature T_2 the temperatures T_1 and T_5 can be calculated by implementing the NTU method in HEX-2.

$$C_{4,5} = \dot{m}_a \cdot C_{p,a}(T_4) \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$C_{1,2} = \dot{m}_a \cdot C_{p,a}(T_2) \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$C_{\min} = \min(C_{4,5}, C_{1,2}) \quad (\text{A.11})$$

$$C_{\max} = \max(C_{4,5}, C_{1,2}) \quad (\text{A.12})$$

$$NTU_{\text{HEX-2}} = \frac{UA_{\text{HEX-2}}}{C_{\min}} \quad (\text{A.13})$$

As a consequence, the efficiency of the heat exchanger ($e_{\text{HEX-2}}$) can be calculated as:

$$e_{\text{HEX-2}} = \frac{1 - e^{-\left(1 - \frac{C_{\min}}{C_{\max}}\right) \cdot NTU_{\text{HEX-2}}}}{1 - \frac{C_{\min}}{C_{\max}} e^{-\left(1 - \frac{C_{\min}}{C_{\max}}\right) \cdot NTU_{\text{HEX-2}}}} \quad (\text{A.14})$$

As a result, the temperatures T_1 and T_5 can be calculated from the following equations:

$$T_1 = \frac{T_4 - \frac{C_{1,2} \cdot T_2}{C_{\min} \cdot e_{\text{HEX-2}}}}{1 - \frac{C_{1,2}}{C_{\min} \cdot e_{\text{HEX-2}}}} \quad (\text{A.15})$$

$$T_5 = T_4 - e_{\text{HEX-2}} \frac{C_{\min}}{C_{4,5}} (T_4 - T_1) \quad (\text{A.16})$$

Following the calculation of the air temperature T_5 , the air temperature T_6 can be obtained from Eq. (40).

As a consequence, the exchanged power at HEX-1 ($Q_{\text{HEX-1}}$) can be calculated from Eq. (26) and therefore for a given inlet temperature at each time from the TES tank, the return temperature can be calculated from Eq. (25). Furthermore, an additional calculation of exchanged power ($Q'_{\text{HEX-1}}$) can be obtained from Eqs. (27)-(28).

As a result, the difference (g_1) between the two calculations of the exchanged power for the assumed air mass flow and pressure ratio can be defined as:

$$g_1(\dot{m}_a, \pi) = Q_{\text{HEX-1}} - Q'_{\text{HEX-1}} \quad (\text{A.17})$$

In the case of convergence g_1 will be zero.

In addition, the power required in the compressor and the power generated in the turbine can be calculated from Eqs. (39), (41). Therefore, the difference (g_2) in the energy equilibrium can be defined as:

$$g_2(\dot{m}_a, \pi) = P_{\text{com}} + Q_{\text{HEX-1}} - P_{\text{tur}} - Q_{\text{HEX-3}} \quad (\text{A.18})$$

In the case of convergence g_2 will be zero.

For the convergence of the algorithm the following objective function (obj) is considered:

$$\text{obj}(\dot{m}_a, \pi) = \sqrt{w_1^2 \cdot g_1^2 + w_2^2 \cdot g_2^2} \quad (\text{A.19})$$

where w_1 and w_2 are the weights of g_1 and g_2 respectively. In our case, the weights of each difference were considered to be the same and equal to 1.

The convergence of the algorithm and the determination of the air mass flow and pressure ratio will be achieved when the objective function is minimized. For that reason, the genetic algorithm was implemented in order to minimize Eq. (A.19).

Therefore, for each time step (different inlet temperature from the TES tank in the HEX-1) the air mass flow and the pressure ratio can be determined and as a result, the air temperature at each state-point of the HTHP, the power required in the compressor, the power generated in the turbine, the required electrical power and the COP of the HTHP can be calculated.

Appendix B – Weather Data

The irradiation and weather data were taken from PVGIS [31] for a typical August week in Komotini Greece (6/8-13/8) and are presented herein. The hourly data were linearly interpolated. The direct normal irradiation, the diffused irradiation and the ambient temperature conditions are taken from official hourly weather data and interpolated as shown in Figs.B.1-B.3.

Figure B.1. Direct normal irradiation with respect to time

Figure B.2. Diffused irradiation with respect to time

Figure B.3. Ambient temperature with respect to time

In Fig. B.4 the resulting global solar irradiation is presented as obtained from the methodology described in section 2.1.

Figure B.4. Global solar irradiation on the tilted surface with respect to time

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Nomenclature

A	Area	[m ²]	<i>Subscripts</i>	
C _p	Specific heat at constant pressure	[J/kg/K]	a	Air
COP	Coefficient of performance	-	amb	Ambient
eff	Heat exchanger effectiveness	-	c	Collector
Ex	Exergy	-	com	Compressor
G	Solar irradiation	[W/m ²]	el	Electric
h	Enthalpy	[J]	HEX	Heat exchanger
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate	[kg/s]	in	Inlet
n	efficiency	-	is	Isentropic
NTU	Number of transfer units	-	l	Load loop
p	pressure	[bar]	out	Outlet
P	Power	[W]	s	Heat sink
Q	Heat	[W]	sol	Solar
T	Temperature	[°C]	t	Tank
U	Heat loss coefficient	[W/m ² /K]	u	Useful
UA	Units of transfer area	[W/K]	w	Water
V	Volume	[m ³]		
<i>Greek</i>				
α	Solar altitude angle	[deg]		
β	Collector tilt angle	[deg]		
δ	Solar declination angle	[deg]		
θ	Incident angle	[deg]		
π	Pressure ratio	-		
ρ	Density	[kg/m ³]		

References

- [1] Brodny, J., & Tutak, M. (2022). Analysis of the efficiency and structure of energy consumption in the industrial sector in the European Union countries between 1995 and 2019. *Science of The Total Environment*, 808, 152052.
- [2] Uusitalo, A., Turunen-Saaresti, T., Honkatukia, J., Tiainen, J., & Jaatinen-Värri, A. (2020). Numerical analysis of working fluids for large scale centrifugal compressor driven cascade heat pumps upgrading waste heat. *Applied energy*, 269, 115056.
- [3] Badieli, A., Akhlaghi, Y. G., Zhao, X., et al. (2020). A chronological review of advances in solar assisted heat pump technology in 21st century. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 132, 110132.
- [4] Chua, K. J., Chou, S. K., & Yang, W. M. (2010). Advances in heat pump systems: A review. *Applied energy*, 87(12), 3611-3624.
- [5] Bellos, E., Arabkoohsar, A., Lykas, P., Sammoutos, C., Kitsopoulou, A., & Tzivanidis, C. (2024). Investigation of a solar-driven absorption heat transformer with various collector types for industrial process heating. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 122665.

- [6] Calm, J. M., & Hourahan, G. C. (2011, August). Physical, safety, and environmental data for current and alternative refrigerants. In Proceedings of 23rd international congress of refrigeration (ICR2011), Prague, Czech Republic (pp. 21-26).
- [7] Zhang, J., Zhang, H. H., He, Y. L., & Tao, W. Q. (2016). A comprehensive review on advances and applications of industrial heat pumps based on the practices in China. *Applied Energy*, 178, 800-825.
- [8] Marchionni, M., Bianchi, G., & Tassou, S. A. (2018). Techno-economic assessment of Joule-Brayton cycle architectures for heat to power conversion from high-grade heat sources using CO₂ in the supercritical state. *Energy*, 148, 1140-1152.
- [9] Marchionni, M., Bianchi, G. & Tassou, S.A. Review of supercritical carbon dioxide (sCO₂) technologies for high-grade waste heat to power conversion. *SN Appl. Sci.* 2, 611 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-020-2116-6>
- [10] Wright, S. A., Pickard, P. S., Fuller, R., Radel, R. F., & Vernon, M. E. (2009, January). Supercritical CO₂ Brayton cycle power generation development program and initial test results. In ASME power conference (Vol. 43505, pp. 573-583).
- [11] Manente, G., & Fortuna, F. M. (2019). Supercritical CO₂ power cycles for waste heat recovery: A systematic comparison between traditional and novel layouts with dual expansion. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 197, 111777.
- [12] Alavi, S. H. F., Soltani, S., Mahmoudi, S. M. S., & Rosen, M. A. (2024). A novel supercritical carbon dioxide combined cycle fueled by biomass: Thermodynamic assessment. *Renewable Energy*, 222, 119874.
- [13] Khan, M. N., Zoghi, M., Habibi, H., Zanj, A., & Anqi, A. E. (2022). Waste heat recovery of two solar-driven supercritical CO₂ Brayton cycles: Exergoeconomic analysis, comparative study, and monthly performance. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 214, 118837.
- [14] Song, J., Wang, Y., Wang, K., Wang, J., & Markides, C. N. (2021). Combined supercritical CO₂ (SCO₂) cycle and organic Rankine cycle (ORC) system for hybrid solar and geothermal power generation: Thermo-economic assessment of various configurations. *Renewable Energy*, 174, 1020-1035.
- [15] Zhao, B., Yao, J., & Su, Y. (2023). Performance response to operating-load fluctuations for Sub-megawatt-scale recuperated supercritical CO₂ Brayton cycles: Characteristics and improvement. *Renewable Energy*, 206, 686-693.
- [16] Hai, T., Lin, H., Chauhan, B. S., Ayed, H., Loukil, H., Galal, A. M., & Yaman, D. (2023). Performance analysis and optimization of a novel geothermal trigeneration system with enhanced Organic Rankine cycle, Kalina cycle, reverse osmosis, and supercritical CO₂ cycle. *Renewable Energy*, 211, 539-562.
- [17] Delsoto, G. S., Battisti, F. G., & da Silva, A. K. (2023). Dynamic modeling and control of a solar-powered Brayton cycle using supercritical CO₂ and optimization of its thermal energy storage. *Renewable Energy*, 206, 336-356.

- [18] Chen, J., Tan, S., Jiaqiang, E., Liao, G., & Zhang, F. (2024). Dynamic performance and control analysis of supercritical CO₂ brayton cycle for solid oxide fuel cell waste heat recovery. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 123556.
- [19] Turja, A. I., Sadat, K. N., Hasan, M. M., Khan, Y., & Ehsan, M. M. (2024). Waste Heat Recuperation in Advanced Supercritical CO₂ Power Cycles with Organic Rankine Cycle Integration & Optimization Using Machine Learning Methods. *International Journal of Thermofluids*, 22, 100612.
- [20] Chen, J., Tan, S., Jiaqiang, E., Liao, G., & Zhang, F. (2024). Dynamic performance and control analysis of supercritical CO₂ brayton cycle for solid oxide fuel cell waste heat recovery. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 123556.
- [21] Fischer, S., Heidemann, W., Muller-Steinhagen, H., Perers, B., Bergquist, P. & Hellstrom, B. (2004). Collector test method under quasi-dynamic conditions according to the European Standard EN 12975-2, *Solar Energy*, 76, 117–123.
- [22] Bellos, E., & Tzivanidis, C. (2017). Parametric analysis and optimization of a solar driven trigeneration system based on ORC and absorption heat pump, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 161, 493-509
- [23] Jiang, J., Hu, B., Wang, R. Z., Deng, N., Cao, F., & Wang, C. C. (2022). A review and perspective on industry high-temperature heat pumps. *Renewable and sustainable energy reviews*, 161, 112106.
- [24] <https://solindarity.eu/>
- [25] UMEZAWA, S., UEDA, K., FUKUSHIMA, R., AMARI, H., SHIMADA, H., & MATSUHISA, T. (2012). Application study of a heat pump producing high temperature and high pressure water for an industrial drying process. *TRANSACTIONS OF THE JAPAN SOCIETY OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERS Series B*, 78(787), 435-439.
- [26] Daghigh, R., Ruslan, M. H., Sulaiman, M. Y., & Sopian, K. (2010). Review of solar assisted heat pump drying systems for agricultural and marine products. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 14(9), 2564-2579.
- [27] <https://www.tvpsolar.com/>
- [28] Duffie, J. A., Beckman, W. A., & Blair, N. (2020). *Solar engineering of thermal processes, photovoltaics and wind*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [29] Y. Goswami, *Principles of solar engineering*, 3rd edition. Boca Raton, Florida, USA: CRC Press, Taylor & Francis Group, 2015
- [30] Solar Keymark, Test Report, 2016, Test report no. 16COL1343, 20170614_TVP_MT_Power_v4_Solar_Keymark_Test_Report.pdf
- [31] Tzivanidis, C., & Bellos, E. (2016). The use of parabolic trough collectors for solar cooling—A case study for Athens climate. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*, 8, 403-413.

- [32] Bellos, E., & Tzivanidis, C. (2023). A detailed investigation of an evacuated flat plate solar collector. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 234, 121334.
- [33] Petela, R. (2003). Exergy of undiluted thermal radiation. *Solar energy*, 74(6), 469-488.
- [34] https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/photovoltaic-geographical-information-system-pvgis_en
- [35] The MathWorks Inc. (2022). Optimization Toolbox version: 9.4 (R2022b), Natick, Massachusetts: The MathWorks Inc.
- [36] <https://www.ebsilon.com/en/>
- [37] Han, S. P. (1977). A globally convergent method for nonlinear programming. *Journal of optimization theory and applications*, 22(3), 297-309.
- [38] <https://www.mathworks.com/help/optim/ug/fmincon.html>
- [39] Lienhard, J. H. (2005). A heat transfer textbook. Phlogistron.